

Highlights

Transfer Learning for Software Vulnerability Prediction using Transformer Models

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- Different ways of employing transfer learning in vulnerability prediction are examined.
- The approach of extracting word embeddings from LLMs to train a separate model achieves superior results.
- The prior knowledge of natural language can be considered neutral in vulnerability prediction.
- Text mining-based vulnerability prediction models benefit from context-aware embeddings.

Transfer Learning for Software Vulnerability Prediction using Transformer Models

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Abstract

Recently software security community has exploited text mining and deep learning methods to identify vulnerabilities. To this end, the progress in the field of natural language processing has opened a new direction in constructing vulnerability prediction (VP) models by employing Transformer-based pre-trained models. This study investigates the capacity of Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT), and Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) to enhance the VP process by capturing semantic and syntactic information in the source code. Specifically, we examine different ways of using CodeGPT and CodeBERT to build VP models to maximize the benefit of their use for the downstream task of VP. To enhance the performance of the models we explore fine-tuning, word embedding, and sentence embedding extraction methods. We also compare VP models based on Transformers trained on code from scratch or after natural language pre-training. Furthermore, we compare these architectures to state-of-the-art text mining and graph-based approaches. The results showcase that training a separate deep learning predictor with pre-trained word embeddings is a more efficient approach in VP than either fine-tuning or extracting sentence-level features. The findings also highlight the importance of context-aware embeddings in the models' attempt to identify vulnerable patterns in the source code.

Keywords: Software security, Deep learning, Transfer learning, Transformer, Vulnerability prediction

1. Introduction

2 The security level of software systems is a major concern for software development
3 enterprises, which want to produce high-quality and secure software free of vulnerabilities.

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4 Security vulnerabilities are weaknesses in the software, which can be exploited by external
5 threats [1]. The number of new common vulnerabilities and exposures (CVEs) that
6 are discovered annually has increased significantly since 2017 and continues its upward
7 trend¹. Therefore, there is a need for techniques capable of identifying vulnerabilities in
8 software and hence, to prevent their exploitation. Vulnerability prediction (VP) refers
9 to the set of techniques that can assist software developers to prioritize their inspection
10 efforts and time by identifying the vulnerable components of a software system.

11 The number of research publications in the field of VP is steadily growing [2]. Those
12 studies mainly propose vulnerability prediction models (VPMs), which aim at classifying
13 the examined software components as vulnerable or not. VPMs commonly comprise ma-
14 chine learning (ML) models, which are fed with software characteristics encoded mainly
15 in the form of software metrics or in textual form (i.e., text mining). Text mining-based
16 models seem to be the most promising ones [3],[4] and have attracted the most research
17 interest, as well [2].

18 Initially, text mining methods utilized the Bag of Words (BoW) technique for repre-
19 senting the source code as a set of words, each accompanied by the number of occurrences
20 or frequency of occurrence in the code [4],[5]. The advances in deep learning (DL) led
21 to the creation of more complex models, which are trained to learn sequential data that
22 consist of large sequences of tokens (i.e., words) of the source code [6],[7],[8],[3],[9]. In
23 this approach, the tokens of the source code are encoded with the so-called word em-
24 bedding vectors using algorithms such as word2vec [10] and then they are given as input
25 into DL models, usually into recurrent neural networks (RNNs) and convolutional neural
26 networks (CNNs).

27 Later studies appeared, which proposed the representation of the source code in text-
28 rich graphs (e.g., Abstract Syntax Trees, Code Property Graphs, etc.) [11],[12] in order
29 to capture more meaningful syntactic and semantic relationships between the tokens than
30 the traditional word embedding techniques (e.g., word2vec, fastText [13], etc.). Those
31 text-rich graphs are fed into graph neural networks (GNNs) that generate the graph
32 embeddings of the analyzed software components and then the produced embeddings are
33 given as input to a ML classifier.

34 Recently, studies using transfer learning to construct accurate VPMs based on text
35 mining have begun to emerge [14],[15],[16]. Since the introduction of the Transformer
36 architecture [17], several pre-trained large language models (LLMs) have been proposed
37 by the leading companies in NLP and Artificial Intelligence (AI) fields, such as the Bidi-
38 rectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) [18] and the Generative
39 Pre-trained from Transformer (GPT) [19]. Those models have acquired a deep under-
40 standing of natural language (NL) through being trained in a primary task, such as the
41 masked language modeling (MLM), and they can be further trained (i.e., fine-tuned) for
42 several downstream tasks (e.g., text classification).

43 Such a downstream task which could benefit from transfer learning is text mining-
44 based VP. Early attempts of using Transformer-based models for VP, examined whether
45 extracting pre-trained Transformer embeddings (most commonly BERT embeddings),
46 instead of using embeddings generated by word2vec or fastText, is beneficial in predicting
47 vulnerabilities [14],[20]. Some other studies proceeded with fine-tuning Transformer-
48 based models on the classification task of VP using a labeled vulnerability-related dataset

¹<https://www.statista.com/statistics/500755/worldwide-common-vulnerabilities-and-exposures>

49 [15],[16]. Most studies that employed pre-trained models for VP compared their approach
50 with previous state-of-the-art methods, and their findings indicated that transfer learning
51 is a promising solution in the field.

52 However, there is a variety of techniques and different directions (i.e., implementation
53 choices) considered when applying transfer learning for tasks related to code analysis
54 in general and VP in particular. First, as mentioned above, the studies in the VP-
55 related literature use different implementation choices to construct Transformer-based
56 VPMs. For instance, some studies use pre-trained models to extract their embeddings,
57 feed them to separate ML models, and train the models on the classification task (i.e.,
58 word embeddings extraction approach) [20], whereas some others train the entire pre-
59 trained model on VP (i.e., fine-tuning approach) [16],[21]. One can also freeze the pre-
60 trained layers, extract the sentence embeddings, and train only the classification head
61 (i.e., sentence-level embeddings extraction approach). Moreover, there are questions as
62 to whether bimodal LLMs that are pre-trained in both NL and programming language
63 (PL), or LLMs solely specialized in coding tasks are more suitable for the task of VP.
64 Overall, it can be argued that there are various implementation choices that can be
65 made during the implementation of transfer learning-based VPMs. However, previous
66 research attempts just presented the model that was derived from their implementation
67 choices, without providing insight on how these choices affected the model performance
68 and which actually played the most important role in the final accuracy of the model.
69 To the best of our knowledge, no research endeavor exists that specifically evaluates the
70 impact of different implementation choices on the predictive performance of Transformer-
71 based VPMs. These questions are of high interest both for practitioners who would like
72 to understand how their implementation choices could affect the VPM performance, and
73 for facilitating further research in the field of VP.

74 To this end, this study aims at answering the aforementioned questions and dilemmas.
75 More specifically, our objective is to explore transfer learning for VP, with the intention
76 to not only check whether there is any benefit to applying transfer learning to VP, but
77 mainly to examine how we can benefit the most by leveraging the utilization of pre-
78 trained Transformer models for this purpose. In other words, the main objective of our
79 work is to examine which of the implementation choices that are fundamental part of
80 the Transformer-based model construction, seem to play a more important role in the
81 model’s accuracy in the downstream task of VP. It is important to shed some light on the
82 field with an empirical evaluation scheme and, therefore, to show which transfer learning
83 methods are most beneficial to VP, thereby assisting future research endeavors in selecting
84 the optimal ones. For instance, our study could guide researchers and practitioners on
85 which of all the pre-trained models that continuously arise to choose for their analyses.

86 To conduct our analysis, we employ the CodeGPT [22] model, which is the pre-trained
87 on code variant of the GPT model, specifically the GPT-2 model, which is the latest open
88 source version of GPT. We also use the CodeBERT [23] model (i.e., pre-trained on code
89 variant of BERT). Briefly, our contributions are summarized as follows:

- 90 • We investigated the two common ways of applying transfer learning in vulnerability
91 prediction: (i) feature-based approach (i.e., embedding extraction), and (ii) fine-
92 tuning approach.
- 93 • We evaluated word embeddings (i.e., an embedding vector per word) and sentence-
94 level embeddings (i.e., an embedding vector per sequence) extraction approaches.

- 95 • We compared the usage of pre-trained on code unimodal models to bimodal models
96 with both programming and natural language understanding.
- 97 • We identified the optimal way of utilizing CodeGPT-2 and CodeBERT in vulner-
98 ability prediction.
- 99 • We compared with several state-of-the-art approaches, including BoW and word2vec
100 embeddings, which, in contrast with Transformer’s embeddings, are not contextual
101 [24], as well as with graph-based models.

102 The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a summary of the
103 existing work in the related literature. Section 3 describes thoroughly our approach, the
104 utilized dataset, our experimental setup, and the evaluation scheme that we follow. In
105 Section 4, we present the results of the conducted experiments, and in Section 5, we
106 discuss our findings and the lessons learned. Section 6 discusses threats to validity, and
107 finally, Section 7 concludes the paper and provides directions for future work.

108 2. Related work

109 In this section, we discuss related work on software VP using ML techniques. We
110 also present the background of the Transformer models, and subsequently, we provide an
111 overview of the previous studies that utilized variants of the Transformer architecture to
112 perform VP.

113 2.1. Vulnerability prediction

114 Vulnerability prediction models are commonly created using ML techniques that uti-
115 lize software attributes as features. The two most widespread input kinds of VPMs are
116 (i) software metrics, and (ii) text features. Shin and Williams [25] examined the capacity
117 of complexity metrics to predict software vulnerabilities. Chowdhury and Zulkernine [26]
118 observed that metrics such as complexity, coupling, and cohesion can be used efficiently
119 to predict vulnerabilities using ML algorithms (e.g., Decision Trees, Naive Bayes, etc.).
120 Kalouptoglou et al. [27] presented a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP)-based approach using
121 several software metrics extracted by static code analysis as features in order to perform
122 cross-project VP with sufficient results.

123 Text mining-based attempts initially represented the source code as BoW, i.e., a set
124 of words along with their frequencies of appearance [5],[28]. Later on, various researchers
125 represented the source code as sequences of tokens (i.e., words), encoded the sequences
126 to numerical vectors, and provided them to DL models suitable for learning sequential
127 data, such as RNNs and CNNs. In particular, Dam et al. [6] trained a Long Short-Term
128 Memory (LSTM) model to learn sequences of tokens represented with numerical vectors.
129 Li et al. [8] proposed a Bidirectional LSTM model, which received as input sequences
130 of code tokens after transforming them to word2vec embeddings. In [9], an empirical
131 evaluation of different techniques for word embedding software components took place,
132 showcasing the efficiency of word2vec.

133 In their study [11], Zhou et al. proposed Devign, a model based on GNNs, for identi-
134 fying vulnerable source code functions. They extracted graphical representations of the
135 source code such as Abstract Syntax Trees (AST), Control Flow Graphs (CFG), Data

136 Flow Graphs (DFG) etc., and through GNNs, they generated graph embeddings of the
137 source code functions. Those embeddings were then fed to a classifier in order to classify
138 the functions as vulnerable or not. Chakraborty et al. [12] presented a DL-based method
139 named ReVeal, where they extracted graphical representations of the source code, specif-
140 ically Code Property Graphs (CPGs) [29]. They fed the CPGs to GNNs to learn the
141 graph embeddings, and then, they used an MLP to classify the functions as vulnerable
142 or not. Through their analysis, they replicated several state-of-the-art methods. Their
143 findings highlighted the failure of the existing approaches to perform accurate VP on
144 real-world data and emerged the need for techniques of greater precision.

145 2.2. Transformer models

146 Bahdanau et al. [30] were the first to propose the attention mechanism in neural
147 machine translation. The encoder-decoder architecture that is commonly utilized for
148 sequence-to-sequence problems deal with the problem of using a fixed-length context
149 vector for the encoding of the input sentences. The decoder then generates an out-
150 put based on the whole encoded vector. This way all the input information has to
151 be compressed into a fixed-length vector hardening the ability of the model to learn
152 long sequences. The Attention mechanism addresses this limitation by putting attention
153 weights for each element of the input sequence. Using Attention, a sequence-to-sequence
154 model can generate a new word by searching on specific positions in the source sequence,
155 which contain the most relevant information [30]. Based on the Attention mechanism,
156 Vaswani et al. [17] proposed the Transformer architecture for dealing with sequence-to-
157 sequence tasks. They demonstrated that Transformer outperformed both in accuracy
158 and in training cost state-of-the-art models, including CNN and LSTM.

159 Radford et al. [19] utilized the innovative Transformer architecture in order to develop
160 OpenAI GPT. They demonstrated a large benefit by pre-training language models using
161 a diverse unlabeled dataset and then fine-tuning them on specific tasks. GPT, which
162 utilized the decoder part of the Transformer, was pre-trained on the task of next word
163 prediction on a unsupervised manner to get a deep understanding of the NL and then it
164 was fine-tuned on a supervised manner on several downstream tasks (e.g., questioning-
165 answering, sentence similarity, etc.) demonstrating clear benefit compared with state-
166 of-the-art methods. Next, Devlin et al. [18] introduced the Google AI pre-trained NLP
167 model called BERT, which utilizes the encoder part of the Transformer architecture. In
168 contrast with GPT, BERT has been pre-trained on the MLM objective, where some to-
169 kens of the input sentences have been masked and then the model is trained on predicting
170 the masked tokens. Similarly to GPT, BERT can be fine-tuned efficiently to several NLP
171 downstream tasks. BERT attracted a lot of interest in the NLP field, being the basis for
172 developing several other models [31],[32],[33].

173 Furthermore, in [34], Facebook AI presented the Bidirectional Auto-Regressive Trans-
174 formers (BART). In their study, Lewis et al. [34] proposed a pre-trained autoencoder for
175 sequence-to-sequence models. Actually they used both the encoder and decoder parts
176 of the Transformer architecture, and they pre-trained a model that demonstrated par-
177 ticularly high accuracy when fine-tuned in text generation tasks. Later on, a few more
178 pre-trained Transformer-based models appeared in the NLP-related literature. Google
179 proceeded with presenting the Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer (T5) model [35] that
180 was based on the standard Transformer architecture, conducting an empirical compari-
181 son of different architectures, objectives, and datasets on several downstream tasks, while

182 Thoppilan et al. provided a Language Model for Dialog Application (LaMDA), which is
183 specialized for dialog [36].

184 *2.3. Transformer models in vulnerability prediction*

185 In an early attempt to employ Transformer models in VP, Bagheri et al. [20] presented
186 a comparison of various Python source code encoding techniques for VP. Specifically,
187 they examined the effectiveness of word2vec, fastText, and BERT embeddings along
188 with an LSTM model. Yuan et al. compared traditional word2vec, fastText, and glove
189 [37] embedding techniques with the embeddings gained from BERT’s code variant called
190 CodeBERT [38]. Their results highlighted the effectiveness of CodeBERT embeddings.

191 VulDeBERT was a study that applied fine-tuning on BERT pre-trained model to the
192 downstream task of VP, succeeding promising results [39]. VulBERTa also managed to
193 surpass several state-of-the-art approaches having pre-trained knowledge of source code
194 [40]. Fu et al. proposed LineVul that was a promising attempt to employ a Transformer
195 model in VP [21]. In particular, they used the attention mechanism of the BERT archi-
196 tecture in order to detect vulnerabilities at line level. In a more recent endeavor, Purba et
197 al. utilized some of the most powerful LLMs to perform vulnerability detection showing
198 promising results in comparison with traditional static code analysis tools [41].

199 *2.4. Beyond state-of-the-art*

200 As opposed to the aforementioned studies, in this paper, we do not intend to propose
201 a new model, but we are interested in how to get the most out of transfer learning in
202 VP. More specifically, we empirically examine how implementation choices that are fun-
203 damental in the Transformer-based model construction process affect the performance
204 of the produced VPMs. Existing research works were limited to introducing a novel
205 Transformer-based VPM, without examining (at least reporting) how their implementa-
206 tion choices affected the model performance. In particular, Bagheri et al. [20] and Yuan
207 et al. [38], were limited to the utilization of pre-trained word embeddings without con-
208 sidering other transfer learning approaches. Furthermore, VulDeBERT [39], VulBERTa
209 [40] and LineVul [21] as well as the study of Purba et al. [41] applied solely fine-tuning
210 without examining whether the utilization of pre-trained embeddings with a common
211 ML algorithm could provide similar or even better results, or without trying to freeze
212 some pre-trained layers and train the rest ones.

213 Concisely, most studies in the VP field that use pre-trained models present an ap-
214 proach without neither explaining nor justifying their choice to use a specific model
215 architecture, a PL, NL or mixed PL and NL - pre-trained model, and a word embedding,
216 sentence embedding or fine-tuning approach. Usually, they do not even specify which
217 pre-trained model variant they use (e.g., unimodal or bimodal CodeBERT). To this
218 end, contrary to previous studies that focused solely on proposing a Transformer-based
219 VPM without examining the implementation choices that lead to improved accuracy, the
220 current study examines different approaches that can be followed during the implemen-
221 tation of transfer learning-based VPMs and attempts to shed some light regarding the
222 suitability and the accuracy of the different variations in the employment of pre-trained
223 Transformer-based solutions for VP. Through this process, the best possible approach
224 for applying transfer learning in the field of VP emerges.

225 **3. Study design**

226 In this section, the entire methodology of the current study is described. Initially,
227 we define the research questions that outline the analysis. Then we present the overview
228 of our methodology and subsequently we provide details for the dataset, the utilized
229 models, the embeddings (i.e., features) - based approaches, the fine-tuning method as
230 well as the training and evaluation procedures we followed.

231 *3.1. Research questions definition*

232 The research goals of the current study can be expressed through the following re-
233 search questions (RQs):

- 234 • **RQ₁**: What is the most effective strategy for leveraging pre-trained Transformer-
235 based models in vulnerability prediction?

236 RQ₁ investigates whether it is better for vulnerability prediction to fine-tune the
237 pre-trained models on this specific task (i.e., fine-tuning approach) or extract their
238 features and learn to classify them (i.e., feature-based approach). In addition, it
239 compares the two feature-based approaches by investigating whether it is better to
240 extract the sentence embeddings to represent the input and train a classifier or to
241 extract the pre-trained word embeddings and train a separate dl predictor.

- 242 • **RQ₂**: How useful is the prior knowledge of natural language in vulnerability pre-
243 diction?

244 RQ₂ is responsible for determining whether transfer learning from models pre-
245 trained in both natural and programming languages (i.e., bimodal pre-training)
246 enhances vulnerability prediction as opposed to models pre-trained exclusively in
247 programming languages (i.e., unimodal pre-training).

- 248 • **RQ₃**: What is the performance gain of the best transfer learning approach that we
249 identified compared to the state-of-the-art approaches in the vulnerability predic-
250 tion literature?

251 RQ₃ compares the optimal model, as identified in the previous RQs, in contrast
252 to some well established state-of-the-art approaches, which are based either on
253 text mining or on graphical representations, and through this process, extracts
254 insightful observations regarding the context-awareness of LLMs and the source
255 code representation format.

256 *3.2. Methodology*

257 This section provides a thorough presentation of the current study’s entire method-
258 ology. In Figure 1 there is the high-level overview of our implementation strategy. It
259 includes three main phases, namely as data preparation, training setup, and model test-
260 ing and comparison. More details about the steps of these phases are provided in the
261 following subsections.

Figure 1: Overview of the overall approach.

262 *3.2.1. Data Preparation*

263 Regarding the utilized dataset, we used the Big-Vul dataset [42] that consists of source
264 code retrieved from public repositories found on GitHub, all written in the C/C++
265 programming languages. This dataset contains real world vulnerabilities that have been
266 reported in the Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVEs) database.

267 For the construction of Big-Vul, Fan et al. [42] developed a tool capable of crawling
268 the public CVE database to gather all the available information of a CVE, including
269 the references linking to the relevant software products, which enabled them to search
270 the products with open-source git repositories [42]. This way, they found vulnerability-
271 related commits and extracted the corresponding changes in the source code in order
272 to get the changed parts between before and after repairing a vulnerability. The parent
273 version of these commits (i.e., version before repairing) is the one that contains the
274 reported vulnerability.

275 Through this process, they managed to create a dataset of 188,636 samples collected
276 from 348 open-source software projects with several vulnerability types included. Specif-
277 ically, the dataset has 10,900 vulnerable methods along with their fixes and 177,736 other
278 neutral (i.e., non-vulnerable) methods that can be considered as clean since no vulner-
279 ability has been reported for them yet. Hence, the dataset has a ratio of vulnerable
280 methods equal to 6.13 %.

281 After fetching Big-Vul dataset, we proceeded with data cleansing. For this purpose,
282 we examined the Croft et al. [43] study, which conducts a quality assessment to remove
283 noise in the data of some well established vulnerability datasets including Big-Vul. Based
284 on their findings, the *Chromium* project had to be removed from the dataset as it was
285 found to reduce the accuracy of the overall dataset by leading the vulnerability prediction
286 models to infer incorrect patterns between classes. In particular, Croft et al. noticed
287 that most of the vulnerability reports related to *Chromium* were improperly traced since
288 its repository is not naturally hosted by GitHub. They validated their observation by
289 showing a large drop in vulnerability prediction models accuracy when removing noisy
290 data from the testing set, indicating to incorrect patterns learnt during the training
291 phase. Therefore, we proceeded to the removal of *Chromium* from both the training and
292 evaluation sets in order to avoid introducing noise when constructing our models.

293 Next, we separated the dataset randomly in three different parts i.e., (i) training,
294 (ii) validation, and (iii) testing parts, following a common evaluation technique in ML
295 and in VP specifically [2]. Specifically, we divided the entire dataset into two sets; one
296 for training and validation and one as a completely unseen set for testing purposes in
297 percentages of 90-10 %. We then divided the large set of 90 % further into training and
298 validation sets, again in percentages of 90-10 %. The training dataset was utilized for
299 the training of the examined models on the vulnerability-related data. The validation
300 set was utilized for evaluating the produced models during the hyperparameter selection
301 phase, whereas the testing set was used as a testbed for the final evaluation of the
302 analyzed approaches, and therefore, for the models' comparison and the conclusions of
303 our analysis.

304 *3.2.2. Training Setup/Setting*

305 In this section, we describe the entire process that we followed to train our models and
306 conduct our experiments. As can be seen in Figure 1, we fed the input training data in
307 the examined models in order to optimise them (i.e., find the optimal hyperparameters),

308 based on their performance on the validation data, and therefore, produce the optimal
309 model per each examined approach.

310 For all the examined transfer learning approaches, we leveraged the pre-trained on
311 code variants of BERT and GPT-2 models, namely as CodeBERT and CodeGPT-2, which
312 have demonstrated promising results for code-related objectives [23],[21],[44]. CodeGPT-
313 2 is based on the GPT-2, which is the latest open-source version of the GPT model that
314 was developed by OpenAI². GPT-2 employs the decoder part of the Transformer archi-
315 tecture and is pre-trained on the primary task of next word prediction. It is more suitable
316 for text generation tasks. In *CodeXGLUE* study [22], Lu et al. presented CodeGPT-2, a
317 variant of GPT-2, which was pre-trained on PL data retrieved from the Java and Python
318 sets of the *CodeSearchNet*³ dataset. This model has the same decoder-only Transformer
319 architecture and pre-training objective (i.e., next word prediction) as the GPT-2 but has
320 prior knowledge of PL. Specifically, there are two versions of it; one that is pre-trained
321 from scratch on PL⁴ and another which uses as a basis the GPT-2 weights and continues
322 its training on the code corpus (i.e., domain adaptive model)⁵. To distinguish them, the
323 latter is mentioned as *CodeGPT-2-Adapted*.

324 On the other hand, CodeBERT is an encoder-only architecture, which, as its name
325 implies, belongs to the BERT variants. BERT was originally pre-trained on the MLM
326 objective. In MLM, the 15% of the tokens sequences is masked and then the model
327 learns to predict the actual values of the masked tokens. An improved variant of BERT
328 is RoBERTa, which is trained on a much larger dataset with a more effective training
329 approach. The architecture of the RoBERTa model is the basis for CodeBERT, which
330 was developed by Microsoft AI. CodeBERT has two variants: (i) the *CodeBERT-base*
331 model⁶, which is pre-trained on natural and programming language pairs (i.e., bimodal
332 data), and (ii) the *CodeBERT-base-MLM* model⁷, which is pre-trained on source code
333 data in the task of predicting the masked tokens in code fractions. The former is pre-
334 trained on documentation and code pairs of the *CodeSearchNet* dataset, whereas the
335 latter is pre-trained on the code corpus of the *CodeSearchNet* dataset.

336 For the two examined Transformer-based models, we used the *Transformers* library
337 that is provided by Hugging Face (HF)⁸. This library provides implementations of several
338 pre-trained NLP models, including CodeGPT-2, and CodeBERT, and also their pre-
339 trained weights. We used the HF library to load the aforementioned models in order
340 both to extract their sentence-level or word-level embeddings and to fine-tune the pre-
341 trained models in the downstream task of VP.

342 In Figure 1, below the training setup phase, there are mentioned the three differ-
343 ent examined approaches for leveraging pre-trained models in VP; (i) fine-tuning, (ii)
344 sentence-level embeddings extraction, and (iii) word embeddings extraction. To begin
345 with, fine-tuning in VP is the process of training on a labeled dataset both the layers
346 of a pre-trained model and an extra classification layer placed on the top of the existing

²<https://openai.com/>

³https://huggingface.co/datasets/code_search_net

⁴<https://huggingface.co/microsoft/CodeGPT-small-py>

⁵<https://huggingface.co/microsoft/CodeGPT-small-py-adaptedGPT2>

⁶<https://huggingface.co/microsoft/codebert-base>

⁷<https://huggingface.co/microsoft/codebert-base-mlm>

⁸<https://huggingface.co/>

347 model (classification head). In fine-tuning, the model adapts its prior language knowl-
348 edge on a specific objective. In this study, we fine-tuned CodeBERT and CodeGPT-2 on
349 the objective of VP, using the vulnerability dataset described in Section 3.2.1. During
350 fine-tuning, the training dataset, in the format of sequences of tokens, is fed to the VPM
351 that consists of the pre-trained Transformer-based model and the classification head, and
352 then, both of them are trained and their weights are updated in order to minimize a loss
353 function, which is the Cross-Entropy loss⁹. Finally, the models learn to classify software
354 components as vulnerable or not.

355 CodeBERT and CodeGPT-2 were fine-tuned using their default Transformer archi-
356 tecture as provided by HF. Specifically, CodeBERT, similarly to RoBERTa, has 12 Trans-
357 former layers with 768 hidden size, 12 attention heads and a total of 125 millions pa-
358 rameters. CodeGPT-2, similarly to GPT-2, has also 12 layers, 768 hidden size, and 12
359 attention heads, but it has 117 millions parameters. We added a classification head and
360 proceeded with training using a learning rate (LR) set as 0.00002 (i.e., 2e-5) along with
361 a linear scheduler where the LR decays linearly during the training procedure. For the
362 optimization of the gradient descent, we used AdamW (Weighted Adam) optimizer [45].
363 The sequences of the input had a maximum length equal to 512, the longest length they
364 are capable of supporting. We employed also the Early Stopping technique to determine
365 the number of epochs. In addition, zero padding was used to ensure that each sequence
366 had the same length throughout the encoding of the textual data using CodeBERT and
367 CodeGPT-2 tokenizers, and the truncation approach was used to trim sequences that
368 exceeded the maximum length.

369 Apart from fine-tuning, we leveraged those LLMs in vulnerability prediction by fol-
370 lowing feature-based approaches. Specifically, we fed to them the input data and we
371 extracted the features of the last hidden layer (i.e., sentence-level embeddings). The
372 extracted embeddings were given then as input to a ML classifier, which actually is a
373 classification layer placed on top of the Transformer model and is called classification
374 head. During training, the pre-trained layers froze and the classification head learnt to
375 classify functions as vulnerable or not.

376 Furthermore, we employed LLMs by extracting their pre-trained word embedding
377 vectors. Word embedding is a method that represents words as vectors of real numbers.
378 These word vectors capture semantic and syntactic information about words, enhancing
379 the capabilities of ML models to learn textual data. A popular word embedding algo-
380 rithm is word2vec [10], which is the method most commonly used in the VP field [2].
381 However, LLMs have proposed a different embedding approach by producing context-
382 aware embedding vectors. During this approach, the way words are used in sequences
383 varies based on their context. This results in a word having different vector representa-
384 tions depending on the context. In our analysis, we transformed the sequences of source
385 code tokens to sequences of contextual (CodeBERT or CodeGPT-2) embedding vectors.
386 These sequences were the input to a DL model, which was trained in binary classification
387 to predict whether a sequence has vulnerabilities.

388 For the selection of the DL classifier, we examined various DL algorithms. We fo-
389 cused mainly on the RNNs, since they are the most capable neural networks (except
390 Transformers) for learning sequential data similar to language data. During training, we

⁹<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cross-entropy>

391 used the validation data in order to configure the optimal hyperparameters of the DL
392 models. After an extensive hyperparameter tuning, we ended up with Adam optimizer,
393 learning rate equal to 0.001, and batch size 64. We applied also the Early Stopping
394 technique to determine the number of epochs before the models start to overfit. To avoid
395 overfitting, we also utilized dropout layers in all layers (both hidden layers and dense
396 output’s dense layer). For the initialization of the weights, the Xavier Initialization was
397 used. We put three recurrent layers (with 500-100-200 nodes respectively) along with the
398 tanh activation function. The loss function utilized was the binary cross entropy with
399 the Sigmoid activation function in the last layer. We also experimented with different
400 kinds of recurrent layers. In particular, we compared several RNN variants including
401 LSTM, Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU), Bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM), and Bidirectional
402 GRU (BiGRU). We also examined 1-D CNNs since they have demonstrated competent
403 performance in VP [2],[3],[9]. It turned out that BiGRU is the best model for our case,
404 at least for Big-Vul.

405 Finally, we used also traditional embedding methods in order to facilitate direct
406 comparison of context-aware embeddings versus static (i.e., global) embeddings, such as
407 word2vec ones. Static vectors represent each word in a unique matter, regardless their
408 particular context. To train static embeddings such the word2vec vectors, we utilized the
409 training set of our dataset. We applied the word2vec algorithm on this set in order to
410 learn source code-aware word2vec static embedding vectors. We then fed the sequences of
411 word2vec vectors to the DL model and we trained it to classify the sequences to vulnerable
412 and non-vulnerable. We repeated the whole process by employing also the fastText
413 algorithm, which, although still produces static vectors, it manages to tokenize also out
414 of vocabulary words, since it acts on sub-word and character level. To train the static
415 word embeddings on C/C++ data, the vector dimension, after several experimentations,
416 was chosen equal to 100 and the context window size equal to 20 words. We utilized
417 Skip-gram and Continuous Bag-of-Words (CBOW) variants for Word2vec and fastText
418 respectively. Last but not least, for reasons of completeness, we proceeded also with the
419 state-of-the-art BoW representation. For the BoW approach, we utilized the Random
420 Forest classifier, which has been widely adopted in the literature of VP [4],[2],[21], often
421 demonstrating high accuracy.

422 3.2.3. Model Testing and Comparison

423 For the evaluation of all the examined techniques, we quantify the produced results
424 using common classification metrics. In particular, we employed accuracy, recall, pre-
425 cision, F_1 -score, and F_2 -score. We consider as the most critical measurement for our
426 analysis the F_1 -score, which considers equally both recall and precision and therefore
427 consists a measurement capable of reflecting the attempt to both increase the actual
428 vulnerabilities identified and to decrease the false positives. It is also the most utilized
429 metric in the VP-related literature [2] and thereby facilitates the comparison with other
430 studies. The mathematical formula of F_1 -score is provided below:

$$431 \quad F_1\text{-score} = \frac{2 \times \text{precision} \times \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}} = \frac{2 \times \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \times \frac{TP}{TP+FN}}{\frac{TP}{TP+FP} + \frac{TP}{TP+FN}} = \frac{2 \times TP}{2 \times TP + FP + FN} \quad (1)$$

432 , where TP stands for True Positives, FP for False Positives, and FN for False Nega-
433 tives.

433 At this point, we have to notice that the experiments (i.e., both training and evalu-
434 ation processes) for each different examined approach were repeated ten times by using
435 a different seed each time, and their average values were calculated and reported. This
436 setting prevents our analysis from depending on the randomness that exists in various
437 processes during data shuffling, model training, computational calculations, etc.

438 4. Results

439 In this section, the study’s experimental results are presented with respect to the
440 three research questions defined in Section 3.1. All the experiments took place on the
441 CUDA¹⁰ platform of a GeForce RTX 4080 Super Nvidia GPU. The results provided are
442 derived from the testing part of the dataset.

443 4.1. RQ₁ - Most effective strategy for leveraging pre-trained Transformer-based models 444 in vulnerability prediction

445 In RQ₁ we examined all the transfer learning approaches that one can follow to
446 leverage LLMs for the downstream task of VP. To this end, we employed the CodeBERT
447 and the CodeGPT-2 models. First, we fine-tuned in VP both of the pre-trained on code
448 *CodeBERT-base-MLM* and *CodeGPT-2* models by updating the weights of all their
449 layers to adapt the models to this particular task. Next, we extracted their embeddings
450 at either sentence or word level and trained DL classification models in VP.

451 In case of sentence embeddings, we fed the input data to pre-trained models, sub-
452 sequently, we froze their pre-trained layers, and therefore the given sequences of tokens
453 were encoded as sentence-level embeddings. Those embeddings were given to the classifi-
454 cation head of the models, which was then trained on binary classification to discriminate
455 vulnerable and non-vulnerable functions. In case of word embedding, we extracted the
456 word embedding vectors from the pre-trained models and provided them to the embed-
457 ding layer of a separate neural network. This way, we utilized the pre-trained models to
458 gain their prior knowledge so as to represent the source code tokens. We then trained the
459 neural network on the binary classification task of VP. Specifically, we trained a BiGRU
460 model, which proved to be the best one among the examined RNNs and the CNN on the
461 Big-Vul dataset, as described in Section 3.2.2.

462 Table 1 summarizes the evaluation results of the three approaches on the testing set.
463 Particularly, it presents the average values of ten different repetitions of the evaluation
464 per case. As can be seen, the word embedding extraction approach is the clear winner
465 among the two feature-based methods. Specifically, word embedding extraction from
466 CodeBERT and CodeGPT-2 leads to a VPM of F₁-score equal to 91.4% and 90.2%
467 respectively, whereas the sentence embedding extraction from these models achieves 67%
468 and 56.8% F₁-scores, which are much lower values. It seems that, by just training the
469 classification head, the models do not manage to capture efficiently the vulnerability
470 patterns.

471 As can be seen in Table 1, the word embedding extraction approach and the fine-
472 tuning approach, are really close to each other, both when using CodeBERT and CodeGPT-
473 2. We can discern a very slight lead of the fine-tuned models but we can not single out

¹⁰<https://developer.nvidia.com/cuda-toolkit>

Table 1: Evaluation results of fine-tuning and feature-based approaches of transfer learning in vulnerability prediction.

Model / Metric (%)	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F ₁ -score	F ₂ -score
CodeBERT fine-tuning	99.0	96.3	87.4	91.6	89.0
CodeGPT-2 fine-tuning	98.8	96.0	85.2	90.3	87.2
CodeBERT sentence embeddings	96.8	98.3	50.8	67.0	56.2
CodeGPT-2 sentence embeddings	96.0	89.8	41.5	56.8	46.6
CodeBERT word embeddings	98.9	96.0	87.4	91.4	88.9
CodeGPT-2 word embeddings	98.8	96.4	84.8	90.2	86.9

Table 2: Number of trainable parameters and training time required for fine-tuning and word embedding extraction approaches.

Model / Metric	Time (s)	Number of Trainable Parameters
CodeBERT fine-tuning	7,091	124,647,170
CodeBERT word embeddings	1,515	4,954,801
CodeGPT-2 fine-tuning	11,336	124,245,504
CodeGPT-2 word embeddings	4,883	4,954,801

474 just one as the best. To facilitate the comparison, we proceeded with conducting a sta-
 475 tistical test so as to identify whether there is a statistical significance in the superiority
 476 of the fine-tuning approach. Specifically, we performed the Wilcoxon-Signed Rank Test
 477 [46], which can judge whether there is a statistically significant difference between two
 478 pairs (i.e., F₁-scores achieved by fine-tuning and by word embeddings extraction). For
 479 this purpose, we used all the ten F₁-scores computed by each model and each approach,
 480 and we utilized them as pairs based on the seed’s value. Based on the Wilcoxon analysis,
 481 we found that the p-values were 0.49 and 0.84 for CodeBERT and CodeGPT-2 respec-
 482 tively, which are higher than the 0.05 threshold, and therefore we cannot state that there
 483 is a statistically significant difference between the two approaches.

484 Nonetheless, Table 2 shows that although the evaluation results of the DL model’s
 485 training on pre-trained embeddings and Transformer fine-tuning approaches are quite
 486 close, there is a important difference in the time required to fine-tune CodeBERT and
 487 CodeGPT-2 models in contrast to the time required to train a DL classifier using the
 488 embeddings of these large models. A great difference between the two approaches ex-
 489 ists also regarding the number of trainable parameters (i.e., model weights), which are
 490 updated during the training process. As can be seen, there is a clear advantage of the
 491 pre-trained embeddings extraction and DL model’s training approach, where the training
 492 process lasts by far less time and the number of weights that need to be updated range
 493 in a lower order of magnitude.

494 In particular, the CodeBERT embeddings method needed 1,515 seconds (less than
 495 half an hour of training) approximately to be completed, whereas fine-tuning CodeBERT
 496 required 7,091 seconds (almost 2 hours of training). Significant difference exists also in the
 497 CodeGPT-2 case. The CodeGPT-2 embeddings-based training of the RNN lasted 4,883
 498 seconds (about 81 minutes), while CodeGPT-2 fine-tuning needed 11,336 seconds (more
 499 than 3 hours). Fine-tuning CodeGPT-2 completed in more time than CodeBERT, since
 500 it usually needed 5 epochs until reaching the optimal F₁-score, while CodeBERT needed
 501 4 epochs. Similarly, the CodeGPT-2 word embedding extraction required more time

502 than CodeBERT embeddings since it was completed after 23 epochs, while CodeBERT
503 needed just 7 epochs. In any case, both models' fine-tuning proved to be a much more
504 time-consuming process than embeddings extraction and DL model's training.

505 Moreover, the CodeBERT embeddings method includes 4,954,801 trainable param-
506 eters that need to be optimized during training, whereas the CodeBERT fine-tuning
507 approach requires the training of 124,647,170 parameters, which is a significantly higher
508 number. In case of CodeGPT-2, the embeddings extraction and DL model's training
509 method needs to update 4,954,801 trainable parameters (i.e., same number as in Code-
510 BERT embeddings, since the trainable parameters regard the DL model, which is com-
511 mon) in contrast with the fine-tuning approach, which includes 124,245,504 trainable
512 weights. Concisely, the results of the analysis suggest that:

513 **The most effective strategy to leverage transfer learning techniques in the
field of vulnerability prediction is the feature-based approach of extracting
the pre-trained word embedding vectors from code-oriented LLMs such as
CodeBERT, use them to represent the sequences of source code tokens, and
train a separate DL model specifically on the task of classifying functions
as vulnerable or not.**

514 4.2. RQ₂ - Contribution of prior knowledge of natural language

515 After identifying in RQ₁ the optimal way of using transfer learning from LLMs to
516 VP, in the context of RQ₂, we examined whether it is preferable to use models pre-
517 trained on unimodal data (i.e., exclusively on programming language) or pre-trained on
518 bimodal data (i.e., both programming and natural language). For this purpose, we em-
519 ployed the fine-tuning and word embeddings extraction approaches presented in Table
520 1, where we used the unimodal versions of CodeBERT and CodeGPT-2, but we also
521 repeated the experiments by retaining the NL knowledge of the models (i.e., bimodal
522 models). Specifically, in the case of CodeBERT, we included in the analysis the bimodal
523 *CodeBERT-base* variant, which is pre-trained on pairs of documents and code. In ad-
524 dition, in case of CodeGPT-2, we utilized the *CodeGPT-2-Adapted* version, which was
525 pre-trained on code data without initializing the already pre-trained on NL weights of
526 *CodeGPT-2*. Table 3, shows the values of the evaluation metrics for all these experiments.

527 The results shown in Table 3, which correspond to the average values of ten different
528 repetitions of the evaluation per case, do not clearly demonstrate an optimal approach.
529 We can see that the F₁-scores (and the other metrics as well) are very close in unimodal
530 and bimodal scenarios, in both CodeBERT and CodeGPT-2 models and in both fine-
531 tuning and word embeddings approaches. Therefore, we conducted the Wilcoxon-Signed
532 Rank Test [46] to decide if there is a statistically significant difference. The p-values
533 among unimodal and bimodal models were 0.49 for the CodeBERT fine-tuning case,
534 0.002 for the CodeGPT-2 fine-tuning, 0.69 for CodeBERT word embeddings, and 0.81 for
535 CodeGPT-2 word embeddings. In three of the four cases, the p-values were greater than
536 0.05, and therefore, we cannot state that there is a statistically significant difference.
537 Only the case of fine-tuning CodeGPT-2 presents a statistically significant difference
538 with a Wilcoxon p-value lower than 0.05. However, it happens only in one case and the
539 absolute difference in F₁-score is quite low (i.e., just 0.9%). Hence, our study cannot
540 yield any clear answer as to which of the bimodal and unimodal pre-trained models is
541 better in VP. It can be argued that:

Table 3: Evaluation results of Transformer models pre-trained solely on source code versus ones pre-trained on bimodal data, when utilized for vulnerability prediction.

Model / Metric (%)	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F ₁ -score	F ₂ -score
unimodal CodeBERT fine-tuning	99.0	96.3	87.4	91.6	89.0
bimodal CodeBERT fine-tuning	98.9	96.6	87.0	91.5	88.7
unimodal CodeGPT-2 fine-tuning	98.8	96.0	85.2	90.3	87.2
bimodal CodeGPT-2 fine-tuning	98.9	95.2	87.6	91.2	89.0
unimodal CodeBERT embeddings	98.9	96.0	87.4	91.4	88.9
bimodal CodeBERT embeddings	98.9	96.1	86.9	91.3	88.6
unimodal CodeGPT-2 embeddings	98.8	96.4	84.8	90.2	86.9
bimodal CodeGPT-2 embeddings	98.8	96.9	84.9	90.5	87.1

The prior knowledge of natural language does not offer a clear benefit in vulnerability prediction but, neither does it act as noise. It can be considered neutral.

4.3. RQ₃ - Comparison with other text mining-based and graph-based vulnerability prediction approaches

In the context of RQ₃, we conducted a comparison of the best transfer learning VP approach that we identified in the previous RQs as opposed to other text mining-based approaches as well as to some popular in the related literature VPMs that are based on graphs. As the best transfer learning method we qualified the unimodal CodeBERT word embedding extraction, which emerged as the optimal (i.e., most accurate and lightweight) one in the previous RQs, considering both the F₁-score and the accuracy-effort trade-off, as presented in Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3.

To answer the first part of RQ₃ (i.e., comparison with other text mining-based techniques), we conducted an experiment to compare the same DL architecture and training paradigm (i.e., word embedding extraction and DL classifier) when (i) using word embeddings extracted from LLMs, and when (ii) employing word embeddings learnt by traditional text mining algorithms. This way, we can demonstrate the advantage of the prior knowledge of the LLMs, which is expressed through the context-aware embedding vectors.

As regards the traditional techniques, we trained the word2vec model in the training part of the dataset, we encoded the input’s sequences with word2vec vectors, we fed them to a DL model, and we trained it on VP. For reasons of completeness, apart from the widely used word2vec [2], we employed more text mining-based models such as the fastText model, which surpasses the out-of-vocabulary barrier of word2vec, as well as the Bag of Words (BoW) method. Table 4 presents the evaluation scores of the examined text mining approaches.

Based on Table 4, CodeBERT word embeddings demonstrated a much higher F₁-score by 55.8%, 59.8%, and 69.4% as opposed to word2vec, fastText, and BoW respec-

Table 4: Comparison of text mining-based vulnerability prediction models.

Model / Metric (%)	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F ₁ -score	F ₂ -score
word2vec	93.2	44.0	29.9	35.6	31.9
fastText	94.3	63.8	21.0	31.6	24.3
BoW	93.0	40.7	15.1	22.0	17.2
CodeBERT embeddings	98.9	96.0	87.4	91.4	88.9

Table 5: Comparison of CodeBERT word embeddings extraction approach versus the graph-based Devign and ReVeal models.

Approach	Dataset	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F ₁ -score
Devign model	FFmpeg+QEMU	58.5	53.6	62.7	57.1
CodeBERT embeddings	FFmpeg+QEMU	60.5	54.8	78.5	64.5
ReVeal model	ReVeal	84.3	30.9	60.9	41.2
CodeBERT embeddings	ReVeal	85.6	36.8	65.2	47.1

569 tively. Actually, they surpassed static embeddings-based approach in all the 5 evaluation
570 metrics. This observation indicates that there is an important benefit from the use of
571 context-aware vectors instead of the global (i.e., static) ones. In other words, the abil-
572 ity of the Transformer-based models to learn, during the pre-training phase, the words
573 syntax and semantics based on their context and to give words different vectors corre-
574 sponding to their context, is an important factor that can enhance the performance of
575 the text mining-based vulnerability prediction models.

576 Furthermore, the purpose of RQ₃ is also to demonstrate whether there is an advantage
577 of the best models (as identified in the previous RQs) as opposed to some of the most
578 powerful and well established in the literature VPMs, which are based on graphical
579 representations of the source code (e.g., CPGs, ASTs, CFGs, etc.). To this end, we
580 employed the Devign [11] and ReVeal [12] datasets and we repeated the CodeBERT word
581 embedding extraction approach, as we did in the Big-Vul case, using the *CodeBERT-base-*
582 *MLM* model. For reasons of completeness, we conducted again the DL model selection
583 process and we ended up with selecting the CNN model as the DL classifier for these
584 two datasets. Table 5 presents the evaluation results of the transfer learning approach
585 in contrast to the Devign and ReVeal approaches.

586 We retrieved the ReVeal scores as they are provided by the ReVeal study[12]. In case
587 of Devign, we reported also its results as provided in ReVeal study, since Devign itself
588 did not provide a replication package. On the other hand, ReVeal provided a replication
589 package not only for itself but also for Devign¹¹. In addition, both ReVeal and our
590 analysis utilized only the FFmpeg and QEMU projects of the Devign dataset (i.e., half
591 of the Devign projects), which were provided as open-source by its authors¹².

592 As can be seen in Table 5, the word embeddings from the pre-trained CodeBERT
593 model, fed in a DL classifier (i.e., transfer learning approach) managed to surpass the
594 popular Devign and ReVeal models, which utilize graphical representations of the source
595 code instead of purely textual data. Although Devign and ReVeal had presented impor-
596 tant improvement over previous (non-transfer learning - based) text-mining approaches,

¹¹<https://github.com/VulDetProject/ReVeal>

¹²<https://sites.google.com/view/devign>

597 CodeBERT word embeddings achieved a 7.4 % improvement over Devign and almost
598 6 % improvement over ReVeal. This observation not only enhances the argument that
599 transfer learning provides a great benefit in VP, but also showcases that by using transfer
600 learning, even solely text mining-based models manage to perform well in VP, achieving
601 comparable or even better results than sophisticated graph-based models.

602 Furthermore, this observation indicates that a potential combination of textual and
603 graphical representation of the source code will provide a real advantage in the VPMs.
604 This could be happened either as an unified Transformer-based model, that will have been
605 pre-trained in a large amount of such multi-modal data or by using ensemble learning of
606 text mining and graph-based models. Finally, the response to RQ₃ can be summarized
607 in the following:

608 **Transfer learning genuinely improves text mining-based VPMs by lever-**
aging the benefits of context-aware embedding vectors, also managing to
609 **outperform graph-based VPMs.**

610 5. Discussion and implications

611 In this paper, we set specific RQs about the capacity of the emerging LLMs on VP,
612 examining the BERT and GPT-2 architectures, specifically their pre-trained on code
613 variants namely CodeBERT and CodeGPT-2, paying particular emphasis on identify-
614 ing the best practices to use them for the downstream task of VP. The results of our
615 experiments demonstrated several insights that need to be discussed. Therefore, in this
616 section, we provide implications for the software engineering community.

617 In Section 4.1, the findings of RQ₁ showed that extracting word embeddings from
618 LLMs and feeding them to a separate classifier achieves better results than extracting
619 sentence-level embeddings and equal results with the fine-tuning method, but requiring
620 a much shorter training time, much less number of trainable parameters, and much less
621 GPU memory compared to fine-tuning. Therefore, considering the trade-off between
622 accuracy and resource consumption, word embeddings extraction seemed to be a better
623 option in VP. For VP, which is not a text generation task that would require a sequence-
624 to-sequence architecture (see Section 2.2), we recommend researchers and practitioners
625 to leverage the LLMs positional embeddings, which encapsulate the deep language un-
626 derstanding of these models, instead of proceeding by default with fine-tuning LLMs, or
627 at least to examine the embeddings extraction approach first.

628 Regarding the potential benefit from models' prior knowledge of NL (i.e., RQ₂), our
629 findings in Section 4.2 suggested that there is not a clear conclusion on the VP task.
630 Considering all the combinations of using CodeBERT and CodeGPT-2 following the
631 fine-tuning and word embeddings extraction approaches, we observed that the F-scores
632 were really closed among the bimodal (i.e., knowledge of both source code and natural
633 language) and unimodal (i.e., only knowledge of source code) versions of the models.
634 Although these results do not suggest that NL acted as noise, we can argue that the prior
635 knowledge of NL proved to be neutral to the accuracy of the models. If future research
636 focuses on increasing the amount of data fed to the models in the pre-training phase,
637 in order to improve their language understanding, we suggest, based on our analysis, to
638 prioritize efforts to collect as much data as possible exclusively for source code. This

639 will result in the construction of lighter VP models with higher accuracy, since it would
640 facilitate a trade-off between neutral NL data and beneficial source code data.

641 As regards the RQ₃, in Section 4.3, we showed the great benefit gained by the context-
642 awareness of the word embedding vectors as opposed to the traditional static (i.e., global)
643 vectors generated by word2vec and fastText. In addition, we showed that the text mining-
644 based models, which utilize pre-trained word embeddings, managed to surpass power-
645 ful state-of-the-art models (i.e., Devign and ReVeal). The results also indicated that
646 leveraging both the power of the pre-trained text-mining models (e.g., CodeBERT and
647 CodeGPT-2) and of models capable of learning graphical representations could improve
648 further the performance of the VPMs.

649 To sum up, we recommend that researchers interested in VP explore all of the im-
650 plications described above and shed more light on the aforementioned topics. We also
651 suggest them to explore further the utilization of LLMs for constructing VPMs, focusing
652 on the use of a code-oriented (either textual or multi-modal) Transformer-based model,
653 such as CodeBERT and CodeGPT-2, for contextual representation of source code to-
654 kens, and on the training of a DL classification model (e.g., RNN), to classify software
655 components as vulnerable or not.

656 6. Threats to validity

657 This section discusses potential threats to the construct, internal, and external valid-
658 ity of our study. By critically evaluating methodological challenges and limitations, we
659 aim to enhance the transparency and reliability of our findings.

660 6.1. Construct validity

661 The validity of the study’s findings could have been affected by the accuracy of the
662 vulnerability-related data used for training and evaluating the developed models. The
663 identification of vulnerability-fixing commits is challenging, as it is possible that some
664 commits may not fully repair the underlying vulnerability or may only address a subset
665 of vulnerabilities within a given software component. Furthermore, there is a small
666 possibility that the data samples that were utilized as non-vulnerable may contain an
667 undetected vulnerability. Thereby, we considered them as neutral.

668 6.2. Internal validity

669 Regarding the internal validity, there is a potential limitation by the specific Trans-
670 former models chosen for the analysis. The selection of CodeGPT-2 and CodeBERT may
671 introduce a selection bias, as it cannot be excluded that other Transformer models or
672 different pre-training techniques could lead to different results. Additionally, we may not
673 have tested all the possible combinations of hyperparameter values. The correlation be-
674 tween the models’ hyperparameters can make it difficult to isolate the effects of individual
675 hyperparameters, which could lead to sub-optimal model performance. To mitigate this
676 risk, the hyperparameter tuning process that we followed was really exhaustive.

677 *6.3. External validity*

678 External validity of this study concerns the use of a dataset restricted to C/C++
679 source code. This narrow focus may restrict the generalizability of the findings to other
680 programming languages. Another external validity threat is the exclusive reliance on
681 open-source code. Open-source projects may differ in terms of development practices,
682 coding styles, and vulnerability patterns compared to proprietary software, potentially
683 reducing the applicability of the findings to commercial software development environ-
684 ments. To mitigate this threat, it would be useful to incorporate data from both open-
685 source and proprietary software projects in the future.

686 **7. Conclusions and future work**

687 In this work, our purpose was to examine the different implementation choices when
688 using transfer learning in the task of vulnerability prediction, and therefore, to highlight
689 the optimal approach. We compared the fine-tuning and sentence-level embedding ex-
690 traction approaches, and we investigated the possible benefits of extracting word embed-
691 dings from pre-trained LLMs so as to feed and train separate DL models in vulnerability
692 prediction. We also examined whether it is better to have LLMs pre-trained on both
693 source code and NL or only on source code for a code analysis task such as vulnerability
694 prediction. Moreover, we compared our best models with state-of-the-art vulnerability
695 prediction models.

696 The analysis demonstrated that, for the downstream task of vulnerability predic-
697 tion, there is no benefit of proceeding with the time-consuming approach of fine-tuning
698 instead of the LLM word embeddings extraction, and therefore, it suggests the latter,
699 which achieves the same accuracy but with by far smaller training cost. Furthermore,
700 regarding the question about the possible advantage of pre-training LLMs on bimodal
701 data (i.e., both on source code and natural language), the study concludes that it is
702 not necessarily beneficial but neither damaging for vulnerability prediction. Finally, this
703 study highlighted the importance of context aware embeddings for representing the source
704 code, which can lead to vulnerability predictors of much higher accuracy than static em-
705 bedding vectors and indicated that a combination of textual and graphical source code
706 representations through a multi-modal model could provide even better vulnerability
707 predictors.

708 Future work includes the interpretability of LLMs in vulnerability prediction as well
709 as the examination of their capabilities in the cross-project evaluation scenario. Regard-
710 ing the former, we aim at applying explainable AI techniques to identify the reasoning
711 behind the vulnerability predictions of the LLMs. For the latter, we are interested in
712 comparing the performance of LLMs to traditional techniques for predicting vulnerabil-
713 ities in software projects that are completely different from the projects that constitute
714 the training dataset.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgments

Work reported in this paper has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Program through the DOSS project, Grant Number 101120270.

Appendix A.

Supplementary material related to this article (e.g., code and data) can be found online [47]: <https://sites.google.com/view/vulgpt>

CRedit authors’ contribution statement

Ilias Kalouptsoglou: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization. **Miltiadis Siavvas:** Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision. **Apostolos Ampatzoglou:** Methodology, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Dionysios Kehagias:** Writing - Review & Editing, Resources, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Alexander Chatzigeorgiou:** Methodology, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Project administration.

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